

Mathematical Representations of Aayushman Singh's Black Hole Theoretical Framework

White Hole Repulsive Gravity

$$\rho = \frac{M}{(V_1 - V_2)}$$

$$M = \rho \times (V_1 - V_2)$$

$$F_A = G \frac{\rho \times (V_1 - V_2) \times m_2}{r^2}$$

If we take the initial volume of the mass from which white hole would emerge to be V_1 and the final volume of the mass to be V_2 . If the initial volume is less than the final volume then their difference would be negative give the density also in negative. Probably giving repulsive gravity.

For the mass of Black Hole M with its Schwarzschild radius its density would be $\rho = \frac{M}{\frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3}$ which is $\rho = \frac{3c^6}{4\pi 8G^3 M^2}$ so as we go deeper into the black hole i.e. from its Schwarzschild radius to its center the ratio of increment in its density to its radius would be

$$\frac{\frac{3c^6}{4\pi 8G^3 M^2}}{\frac{2GM}{c^2}} \quad \text{which is} \quad \frac{3c^8}{4\pi 8G^4 M^3}$$

Suppose, we know the distance between the Star and the Black Hole(former Star). The black hole bends the space time, also bending the path or light itself towards it. We can get momentum and energy of the light. Now using the Einstein's formula $E = (pc)^2 + (mc^2)^2$ we can get a mass of the same energy and momentum. Using energy we get a new mass M. Then substituting this value of M in $F = G \frac{m_1 \cdot m_2}{r^2}$. If, we are knowing the mass of the parent star of Black Hole. That would be singularity's mass and we know the distance between them

$$F_A \propto \frac{1}{V},$$

$$F_A \propto M,$$

$$F_A \propto$$

\therefore The Formula becomes :

$$\oint \rho = G \frac{m_1 \cdot m_2}{r^2}$$

Now, if we target the process of Gravitification(or Gravitational collapse) by a stimuli or hypothetically or simply predict the star. Knowing the mass and distance between the Parent Star and the other star would give us the value of $\oint \rho = G \frac{m_1 \cdot m_2}{r^2}$. Knowing this, we could approximately calculate or know that whether a mass inside black hole according to my Energy depth scale Hypothesis makes a new

matter or step into a finite inter atomic fission, where if one atom once gone is torn apart into energy.

Probability is also of that if all matter gets converted in energy then that energy would be inside the event of horizon in the form of heat or other forms of a body which is flowing sea of energy (mixture of different forms of energy) which I had named Man's Lorry (a region of flowing energy).

Inside Man's Lorry in its heart is a region of dense condensed energy which is called singularity, a negligible volume but very heavy mass. My model is this:

Where, the small red star is singularity and the lavender body is Man's Lorry with its circumference as Event of Horizon.

As, we know ;

Schwarzschild radius is : $r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$

Also $\rho \propto \frac{1}{r^3}$,

Volume of a sphere is $\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3$

Substituting the Schwarzschild radius in this would make it $\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3$

$$\rho = \frac{M}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)^3}$$

,

$$\rho = \frac{3c^6}{32\pi G^3 M^2}$$

Then the ratio of $\frac{\rho}{r}$ increment (S_f) as we go deeper into the black hole is

$$\frac{\rho}{r} \text{ increment} = \frac{\frac{3c^6}{4\pi, 8G^3M^2}}{\frac{2GM}{c^2}}$$

$$\frac{\rho}{r} \text{ increment} = \frac{3c^8}{4\pi 8G^4M^3}$$

ρ at a radius lesser than r_s :

$$\rho(r) = \rho_s \times S_f \times \frac{(r_s - r)}{r_s}$$

$$\rho(r) = \frac{3c^6}{4\pi, 8G^3M^2} \times \frac{3c^8}{4\pi, 8G^4M^3} \times \frac{(r_s - r)}{r_s}$$

$$\rho(r) = \frac{3c^6}{4\pi, 8G^3M^2} \times \frac{3c^8}{4\pi, 8G^4M^3} \times \frac{(r_s - r)}{r_s}$$

$$dr = \frac{r_s - r}{r_s}$$

$$\rho(r) = \rho_s \times S_f \times dr$$

So, this tells us density at a certain distance deep into Black Hole from Event of Horizon.